

3-D BRAIDED/RTM COMPOSITES:

SMART RTM FABRICATION & COMPRESSION STUDY

Elvin S.M.Chia

DSO National Laboratories, 20 Science Park Drive. S(118230). Republic of Singapore

Frank K.Ko

Fibrous Materials Research Center, Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA 19104, USA

ABSTRACT: Compression study was conducted to evaluate the mechanical performance of 3-D braided composites made via a smart RTM technique. Two different grades of E-glass fibers and two different epoxy resin systems were selected for studies. The braided/RTM specimens were tested using the IITRI's shear-loading test method. The experimental results, including the stress-strain curves, compressive moduli and strengths, poisson's ratios and failure behavior, are presented and discussed.

KEYWORDS: 3-D Braiding, Smart RTM, Braided/RTM Composites

1. INTRODUCTION

3-D braiding has the capability to fabricate near net-shaped preforms of desired structural part, while providing the required fiber reinforcement. In combination with a resin infiltration process, such as resin transfer molding (RTM), it provides the capability of producing high quality composites with improved tolerance and resistance. Consequently, there is interest in the design, manufacture, and performance characterization of 3-D braided/RTM composites. In particular, because of the non-linear yarn geometry in 3-D architecture, there is a need to investigate the compression properties of these materials, which can be sensitive to the fabrication method used in making the composites. This study was initiated to evaluate the compressive performance of 3-D braided composites made via a smart RTM technique.

2. COMPRESSION TEST

The IITRI test method ^[1-2], developed by Illinois Institute of Technology Research Institute, was adopted in this study. As shown in Figure 1, the IITRI test fixture uses linear bearings and hardened steel shafts to ensure co-linearity of load path. Load is applied to the specimen through serrated wedge grips, which are matched in rigid steel bases.

Fig 1. IITRI test fixture & compression test specimen

3. MATERIALS

3.1 Fiber

Two different fibers sponsored by Owens Corning were selected as reinforcement: 111A-AA-675 and 366-AA-675. The properties of the E-glass fibers (Table 1) used in the theoretical analysis are data extracted from Engineered Materials Handbook [3].

Table 1. Properties of Engineering Fibers

Properties	Units	E-Glass	S2-Glass	T-300	Kevlar-49
Fiber Diameter	Inch	0.00036	0.00036	0.0003	0.00046
Density	g/cm ³	2.58	2.46	1.76	1.44
Tensile Strength	Ksi (MPa)	550 (3450)	665 (4585)	530 (3654)	525 (3620)
Young's Modulus	Msi (GPa)	10.0 (69)	12.6 (86.8)	33 (231)	18 (124)
Poisson Ratio	-	0.22	0.23	0.20	0.34
Break Elongation	%	N.A.	5.4	1.58	2.6

3.2 Matrix

The resin systems selected for studies were Ciba's epoxies, Resinfusion™ 8603R/H and 8607R/H. The reasons for the selection of these resin systems are their ease of processing (i.e., viscosity, gel time, curing process, etc.) and reasonable level of mechanical properties. The properties and characteristics of the resins are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Neat mechanical properties of Resinfusion™ Epoxies

Properties	Resinfusion™ 8603R/H	Resinfusion™ 8607R/H
Hardness (Shore D)	82	86
Ultimate flexural strength (MPa)	97.9	93.5
Flexural modulus (GPa)	2.76	2.29
Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	58.6	64.3
Tensile modulus (GPa)	2.76	2.58
Ultimate compressive strength (MPa)	116.6	228.8
T _g (°C)	74	173
Density (g/cc)	1.09	1.09

Resinfusion™ 8603 R/H and 8607 R/H are specially formulated by Ciba Specialty Chemicals Corporation (Ciba) for use in the production of advanced composites using VARI, RTM, SCRIMP or other liquid infusion process. Their low-mixed viscosity and wet-out potential greatly enhance the ease of processing. The resin is able to cure to self-support after 24 to 48 hours at ambient temperature. In the case of Resinfusion™ 8607 R/H, the curing time can be reduced to 6 hours if processed at about 50°C.

The processing characteristics of Resinfusion™ 8603R/H and 8607R/H epoxies are presented in Table 3. The viscosity of the resin is an important factor in determining a desirable processing condition [4]. If the viscosity is too high, the resin will not flow easily and may not

penetrate fiber bundles, giving poor wet out. If the viscosity is too low, the resin may follow a path of least resistance and leave voids or dry spots. As a rule of thumb, the resin viscosity for use in RTM is recommended to be below 500cP. For 8603R/H, the resin system has a low initial viscosity of below 500cP upon mixing at 25°C. For 8607R/H, the resin system has an initial high viscosity of above 500cP at 25°C. However, the viscosity can be reduced to less than 300cP upon heating to 50°C while maintaining appreciable working time.

Table 3. Processing characteristics of Resinfusion™ epoxies

Resinfusion™ 8603 R/H	
Mix Ratio, (% by weight)	100:15 (Resin:Hardener)
Color	Transparent
Viscosity (cP) @ 25 °C	< 500 for about 40 mins
Gel time (mins) @ 25 °C	80-160
Resinfusion™ 8607 R/H	
Mix Ratio, (% by weight)	100:35 (Resin:Hardener)
Color	Off-white
Viscosity, (cP) @ 25 °C	> 500
Viscosity, (cP) @ 49 °C	< 500 for about 30 mins
Gel time, (mins) @ 25 °C	670
Gel time, (mins) @ 49 °C	30-60

Determination of isothermal viscosity profiles

The isothermal viscosity sweeps at ambient temperature (about 25°C) and elevated temperature (50°C, 60°C and 70°C) were established for Resinfusion™ 8603R/H and 8607R/H respectively using the Brookfield rotating spindle viscometer. From the isothermal viscosity profiles shown in Figure 2, the working times with viscosity of less than 500cP for Resinfusion™ 8603R/H at 25°C and for Resinfusion™ 8607R/H at 50°C respectively are more than 30 minutes.

Fig 2. Isothermal viscosity profiles of Resinfusion™ 8603R/H & 8607R/H

4. BRAIDING LOOM SIZING & PREFORM FORMATION

The braiding loom parameters (numbers of tracks and columns) required for the formation of braided preforms were determined based on the following given information: cross-sectional area (A_C), yarn bundle size (A_Y), braiding angle or known as surface angle (θ), fiber volume fraction (V_f) and track/column movement ratio (k). A braid design code, *3D-TexComp* was developed to perform numerical calculation to determine the braiding loom size or the numbers of columns and tracks in the form of Cartesian grid. Input data for the loom sizing is shown in Figure 3. Since the calculated values (N_y , C , T) are in real number and are rounded off or down to the nearest integer, it should be noted that the fiber volume fraction is slightly different from the desired values.

Fig 3. Input/Output data for sizing of braiding loom

In the formation of braided preforms (5" x 0.5" x 0.125") with $\pm 20^\circ$ surface braid angle, 33% longitudinal fills and 55% fiber volume fraction, a Cartesian grid with 12 columns and 5 tracks (12 x 5 loom size) was required. The Cartesian loom set-up is shown in Figure 4.

Fig 4. Formation of preform for compression coupon specimen

The preform was constructed using the 4-step process^[3,5], by moving the tracks left and right and the columns up and down, which forms an orthogonal interlacing of yarn, and followed by a beat-up motion. The orientation of yarns in the 3-D braided structure was controlled by the tracks-to-columns movement ratio and the tightness of braid formed during the beat-up motion. During braiding, extreme care was taken to minimize the fiber damage and to preserve the desired surface angle. A 35 inches long fabric strip was braided for each braiding operation. These braided strips were subsequently cut into 5 to 6 pieces of preforms of length 6-7 inches each for resin impregnation.

5. SMART RTM TECHNIQUE

In the impregnation stage, the braided preforms were consolidated with resin via a closed mold RTM process. Using a smart RTM technique, a real time feedback and process control system was incorporated to provide in-situ monitoring and flow control of the resin during the entire RTM operation. Unlike conventional RTM method which is either a pressure controlled or flow-rate controlled process, both the pressure and flow-rate are monitored and regulated in the smart RTM technique.

Fig 5. 2100cc RTM injector and real time displays

Figure 5 shows the primary features of Radius Engineering Incorporation's 2100cc RTM injector. By integrating the RTM injector with computer and Floware™ software, the RTM system was tailored to provide real time displays (Figure 5) and control of injection process parameters. The Cylinder Display allows the operator to easily monitor the flow rate and injection or hydrostatic pressure during the RTM process. Volume of resin remaining in the cylinder and volume of resin injected can also be monitored. The display is animated and will show the piston movement according to operator commands. The Tool Display allows the operator to easily monitor the temperatures of tool. The pressure and timer are also displayed. The status bar at the bottom will inform the operator if the resin is cured or not according to a time entered by the operator. The display is also animated and will show the tool fill as resin is transferred in. With the use of Floware™, useful chart (Figure 6) displaying the pressure, flowrate and temperature history in the making of the composite part can also be generated.

Depending on the resin systems used, the injection parameters and curing time varied. While 8603R/H resin was processed and cured at ambient temperature, 8607R/H resin was processed and cured at 50°C. Figure 6 shows the RTM set-up and the typical injection processing parameters for the making of compression coupons. In a typical successful injection, the tool/inlet and cylinder/outlet pressure reached an equilibrium of hydrostatic pressure (Figure 6) at the end of the RTM operation when the mold was being 100% filled.

Fig 6. Set-up of smart RTM process & typical injection processing parameters

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) pictures (Figure 7) of the specimen width's X-section were conducted to examine the quality of the composites. Only good quality specimens with complete fiber wetting were accepted for testing.

(a) Specimen with void (b) 3D specimen with complete wetting

Fig 7. SEM pictures of 3-D braided/RTM specimens

6. TEST RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The 3-D braided/RTM specimens were tested to failure under compressive loading by using Instron Model 4280 machine with a 1.50 mm/min crosshead speed (Figure 1). Table 4 summarizes the compression test results.

Table 4: Compression Test Results of 3-D Braided/RTM Composites

Materials	Resinufusion™ 8603 R/H			Resinufusion™ 8607 R/H		
	Moduli (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Poisson Ratio	Moduli (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Poisson Ratio
111A-AA-675 Fiber	40.70	449	0.478	30.94	501	0.388
366-AA-675 Fiber	33.46	357	0.549	35.50	498	0.457
	Moduli (msi)	Strength (ksi)	Poisson Ratio	Moduli (msi)	Strength (ksi)	Poisson Ratio
111A-AA-675 Fiber	5.903	65	0.478	4.487	72	0.388
366-AA-675 Fiber	4.852	52	0.549	5.149	72	0.457

6.1 Stress-Strain Relationship

Figure 8 shows the typical stress-strain response for the 3-D braided/RTM composites in compression. All the E-glass/epoxy composites with 33% of longitudinal fills behaved in a linear manner to failure.

Fig 8. Typical stress-strain response for 3-D braided composite in compression

Figure 9 shows the average compressive stress-strain responses of the 3-D braided/RTM composites from five replications. For a comparison, the average compressive stress-strain responses of 2-D and 2.5D specimen types established in a separate study are also included.

Fig 9. Average stress-strain responses of braided composites in compression

From Figure 7, it can be seen that with the exception of 111A/8603 specimens, there is no significant differences in the stress-strain responses of the 3-D braided/RTM specimen types made using different fibers (111A-AA-675 and 366-AA-675) and resin systems (Resinufusion™ 8603R/H and 8607R/H). The exceptional behavior of 111A/8603 and discrepancies in the test results could be attributed to the followings: material fabrication practices adopted by personnel, lack of control of fiber alignment during braiding, damage induced by improper coupon sanding during preparation, flatness and parallelism of the tabs during bonding etc.

6.2 Compressive Modulus

The average compressive modulus of the E-glass/epoxy, determined from the stress/strain curves within the 0.1-0.5% strain range, was found to be in the range of 30GPa to 40GPa (4.5 to 5.9 msi). In a similar compression study of 3-D braided composites conducted by David Liao [2], the normalised (w.r.t. 33% fill) compressive modulus of S2-glass/epoxy ($\theta = 20^\circ$, $V_f = 0.5$, 25% fill) made using SCRIMP process was about 37.0 GPa (5.40 msi).

6.3 Compressive Strength

As a matrix-dominant property, the compressive strength of the composites was found to be sensitive to the neat resin property. The ultimate compressive strength of neat 8607R/H resin is 228.8MPa, which is about 2 times higher than that of the neat 8603R/H resin with only 116.6MPa. The compressive strength of 111A/8607 and 366/8607 specimens were therefore found to be superior to that of 111A/8603 and 366/8603 specimens respectively. From the test results, specimens made using 111AA-AA-675 fibers were found to have higher compressive strength than specimens made using 366-AA-675 fibers.

The average compressive strength of the 3-D braided/RTM E-glass/epoxy was found to be in the range of 360 MPa to 500 MPa (52 to 72 ksi). In comparison, the normalised compressive strength of the 3-D braided S2-glass/epoxy composites made using SCRIMP process reported in David Liao [2] work was about 468 MPa (67.0 ksi).

6.4 Poisson's Ratio (ν_{xy})

The average poisson's ratio of the 3-D braided/RTM E-glass/epoxy was found to be about 0.39 to 0.55. The normalised poisson's ratio of S2-glass/epoxy in David Liao [2] work was 0.37.

Fig 10. Compression properties of 3-D braided/RTM E-glass/epoxy composites

Figure 10 summarizes the tested properties with standard deviation of the 3-D braided E-glass/epoxy from the compression study. The compression properties of the E-glass/epoxy made using the smart RTM technique were found to be comparable to that of S2-glass/epoxy consolidated using SCRIMP process [2]. This suggested that the qualities of composites, and hence their mechanical properties, can be sensitive to fabrication methods.

6.5 Failure Behavior

The general compressive failure behavior of 3-D braided composites can be identified as shown in Figure 11. The matrix resin between the fibers first cracked under the compressive loading before final fiber breakage. The micro cracking of the matrix resin in between the fibers occurred prior to catastrophic fiber breakage. For a comparison, the compressive failure picture of a 2-D braided composite is also presented, which unlike its 3-D counterpart, shows the main cracking line generally inclined along the braiding angle.

Fig 11. Typical failure appearances of 3-D and 2-D braided specimens

6.6 Experimental vs Theoretical

The mechanical properties of 3-D braided composites depend on the fiber and matrix properties, fiber volume fraction and fiber orientation. Using the Fabric Geometry Model (FGM) developed by Ko et al [3,5], a unit cell model can be established and its parameters be related to structural performance. For a given braiding angle θ , loom parameters C and T, and specimen cross-section, the unit cell parameters θ' , h, w and t of compression specimen can be computed (Figure 12) and are used for determining the elasticity matrix of the 3-D composites.

W, Width of Braided Composites	= 0.500"
U, Thickness of Braided Composites	= 0.125 "
θ , Braided Surface Angle	= 20
C, No. of Moving Columns	= 11
T, No. of Moving Tracks	= 4
w, unit cell width	= $2*W/C = (2 \times 0.5) / 11 = 0.09091"$ (2.309 mm)
t, unit cell thickness	= $2*U/T = (2 \times 0.125) / 4 = 0.0625"$ (1.588 mm)
h, unit cell height	= $w/(\tan \theta) = 0.250"$ (6.35 mm)

Fig 12. Unit cell of 3-D braided specimens

Comparing the stress-strain responses between the theoretical and experimental results (Fig 9), the FGM's predictions show reasonably good agreement with the experimental data.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Compression study was conducted to evaluate the mechanical performance of 3-D braided/RTM composites. Two different E-glass fibers (111A-AA-675 & 366-AA-675) and two different epoxies (Resinfusion™ 8603R/H & 8607R/H) were evaluated. A design software code, *3D-TeXComp* was used to determine the size of a Cartesian loom to make the braided preforms. Consolidation of the preforms was done using a smart RTM technique. The specimens were tested using the IITRI shear-loading test method.

The compression study revealed that the 3-D braided/RTM composites with 33% longitudinal fills behaved in a linear manner to failure. The general compressive failure behavior of 3-D braided composites can be characterized by initial micro cracking of the resin in between the fibers, prior to final fiber breakage. The test results show that with the exception of 111/8603 specimens, there is no significant difference among the compression modulus of the 3-D braided specimen types. With better neat resin property, the compressive strength of 111A/8607 and 366/8607 specimens were found to be superior to that of 111A/8603 and 366/8603 counterparts respectively.

The compression properties of the 3-D braided/RTM E-glass/epoxy were also found to be comparable to that of S2-glass/epoxy consolidated using SCRIMP process. This can be attributed to the smart RTM technique which ensure good wetting of the test specimens. The choice of composite processing method is therefore deemed a key factor in producing quality composites with superior mechanical properties.

8. REFERENCES

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